

MESA+ INSTITUTE

Revolutionising Semiconductor Manufacturing: MESA+'s Advanced Research Capacities Elevate Global Chip Production Standards

Best practice category

Strengthening manufacturing capacities & Partner collaboration and open ecosystems

Stakeholder group

Academic and Research Institutions

Value chain position

Research and Development & Manufacturing

General Information

The MESA+ Institute for Nanotechnology, situated at the University of Twente (the Netherlands), stands out for its lead in innovation in the semiconductor manufacturing sector. Established in 1981 as MESA, it rebranded as MESA+ with the inclusion of the research group on Electronics, Optics and Materials in 1999. Founded with the vision of merging fundamental and applied research, MESA+ has grown to become one of the world's leading nanotechnology research institutes. With a state-of-the-art NanoLab, courses in complex photonics systems, and a collaborative ecosystem that fosters interdisciplinary research, MESA+ is pioneering advancements in semiconductor materials, devices, and manufacturing technologies.

MESA+ is acknowledged here for setting a Best Practice in the Strengthening manufacturing capacities category, through its dedication to cutting-edge research and development in nanotechnology and its applications in semiconductor fabrication. Its collaborations with other research institutes and participation in clusters led to its distinction in the Partner collaboration and open ecosystems category.

Activities and best practices

MESA+'s role in advancing semiconductor manufacturing is underscored by several significant technological contributions and collaborations.

Firstly, MESA+ NanoLab cleanroom is a cornerstone for micro- and nanofabrication activities, supporting a wide range of academic research, company R&D, and education. It is renowned for its open-access infrastructure, offering five specialised process platforms: Electronics, 3D nano-shaping, Photonics, MEMS/ NEMS, and Fluidics. The facility not only provides essential equipment and training but also aids in research design and process development. This setup fosters a unique environment for innovation and collaboration among academic researchers and industry professionals alike.

MESA+ has been at the forefront of Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) research, developing techniques that allow for the precise control of thin-film materials at the atomic level. Particularly, it has focused on atmospheric-pressure ALD, a method pivotal for creating ultrathin, conformal films with exceptional thickness control. Their research spans various applications, including the production of large-area displays or emerging uses of atmospheric-pressure ALD in high-porosity/3D materials.

Furthermore, the institute has made breakthroughs in silicon photonics, enabling the integration of optical devices on a silicon chip. MESA+ researchers are at the forefront of Organ-on-Chip (OoC) research, which enables the development of chips that mimic the environment of the human body and grow human organs that exhibit mechanical functions. This enables the study of effects of medication, development of faster and personalised treatment, and will minimise the need for animal testing in the future.

Moreover, MESA+ entrepreneurial culture has birthed 30+ spin-off start-ups that develop market-ready nanotechnology services and products. The Institute also collaborates with established companies, like Philips, ASML, LioniX and Thales to develop solutions for industries. Moreover, MESA+ is involved in several regional, national and international associations and clusters active in nanotechnologies or science more broadly. Among these, Nano4Society brings together leading Dutch technological universities to work on projects in e.g. health and agrifood. In addition, NovelT is a non-profit organisation co-founded by the University of Twente that challenges entrepreneurs with innovative ideas to start, innovate, and grow through programs, 1-on-1 coaching, and events.

Finally, as part of University of Twente's academic activities, the Institute also offers advanced courses in Optics, Nanophotonics, and Nanophotonics Experiments as part of the Complex Photonic Systems (COPS) chair. Researchers perform advanced research on propagation and emission of light in complex nanophotonic metamaterials, investigating new physical concepts and developing state-of-the-art techniques. COPS also maintains an extensive repository of articles on photonics prepared by its students and faculty members, as well as publicly available PhD theses reaching as far back as 1988.

Challenges addressed with this practice

MESA+'s focus on bridging the gap between basic science and industrial application has positioned it as a key player in the evolution of semiconductor manufacturing processes, contributing to more efficient, sustainable, and high-performance semiconductor devices. Through its research in domain-specific applications like health, the institute is pushing the boundaries of chip miniaturisation and performance. Finally, by fostering an environment of collaboration and innovation, as well as its involvement in tech clusters, MESA+ Institute is significantly advancing the capabilities of semiconductor research and manufacturing.